

Role of Association Democracy Reform, Special Reference to Lok Sabha Elections 2019

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Abstract:

India accepted parliamentary democracy. In a parliamentary democracy, the people's representatives are directly elected by the people. The members have to have the ability to have a deliberative discussion on the question of the people in the House. The issue of constituency should be brought to the notice of the House. All national level parties, regional parties and local level parties participate in the general elections. All political parties field their candidates. In general elections, the moral path is followed by the immoral path. Violation of code of conduct by a political party candidate during election period. When all the political parties declare their candidates, the candidature is given to the candidate who has the ability to get elected. The candidate's qualifications are dominated by money, power and caste. Candidates are given tickets as candidates even if their background is criminal. The candidate distributes alcohol, cash, money and free items to the people to win the election. Many unethical ways are used in elections to defeat a rival candidate. As a result, the number of candidates with criminal background in the Parliament of India and the Legislative Assembly of each constituent state is increasing day by day. Candidates who are millionaires are also seen winning the elections. But unfortunately considering the educational qualifications of the members of the Indian Parliament and the constituent state legislatures, the situation of the people's representatives is very bad. Which was expected by the organizers? Contrary to that expectation, the situation is that of a people's representative. The general Indian public thinks that our people's representative should be highly educated, honest, self-sacrificing but in reality the people's representatives in our Parliament and the constituent state legislatures are rich, have criminal background and have minimum educational qualifications.

Keyword: parliamentary , ADR , Assets , representative , honest, constituent

Objectives:

1. To Explore the role of ADR in strengthening Indian democracy.
2. To Find out the number of criminal figures in politics
3. To Educational qualifications of candidates belonging to political parties Criminal background Financial background detection

Research Methodology:

The information for this paper has been secondary sources Books, Journal, Government reports and Internet

Establishment of ADR :

ADR was founded in 1999. Indian Institute of Management I. I.M. A group of professors from Ahmedabad and Bangalore filed a PIL in the Delhi High Court. The purpose of the petitioners was to know the criminal financial and educational background of the contesting candidate. The Delhi High Court has directed the Election Commission to make public the background information of the people's representative or candidate. Appealed in the Supreme Court against the decision of the Delhi High Court. In 2003, the Supreme Court made it mandatory for all contesting candidates to disclose their criminal, financial and educational background by filing an affidavit with the Election Commission of India before the election. This decision helped in creating awareness among the voters about the criminal case against the people's representative.

Founding member of ADR :

The Association Democracy Re-Form was established in 1999 with Trilochan Shastri Jagdish S Chhokar Ajit Ranade Sunil Handa Devnath Tirupati Bridge Kothari Rajesh Agrawal Pankaj Chandra Sudarshan Khanna Prem Pagotra PR Shukla The role of Major General Anil Verma etc. was important due to the contribution made by him.

The main objective behind the establishment of Association Democracy Reform:

1. Strengthening Indian democracy
2. Reforming Indian politics
3. Trying to improve the electoral system
4. Reducing the influence of criminal violence in politics
5. Ending corruption in politics
6. Freeing political sector criminals
7. To make the political party accountable to the people
8. Determining the jurisdiction of a political party
9. To strive for democracy within political parties
10. Candidate's educational qualification, criminal financial background to be made public

ADR's work and research area :

1 Election Watch

Election Watch is the flagship event of ADR. Election Watch has been held across the country since 2002. The affidavits of the contesting candidates are scrutinized. Citizens are given detailed information about the background of the

candidates. So as to help them in choosing a voter. Election Watch has so far collected data of 1,82,108 candidates.

2 ADR has also analyzed the election expenses of the elected representatives.

Political Party Watch P.P.W. National and regional party IT returns are analyzed. Shows an analysis of their income tax returns and donation statements filed with the Election Commission of India. The ADR analyzed the sources of funding for six national and 51 regional political parties.

3 The main objective of ADR's PPW program is to bring transparency in the functioning of political parties.

ADR succeeded in making public the ITR of the political party. All funds beyond the cash received by the political party up to Rs.

4 The Supreme Court of India has made it mandatory for candidates contesting elections to Members of Parliament and State Assemblies to file an affidavit, Form 26, disclosing all their criminal, financial and educational information. This decision was implemented by all the State Election Commissions at the Conference of State Election Commissioners of India held in July 2003 in the local body elections.

5 N.O.T.A. in EVM machine since 2014 Lok Sabha elections in Electronics Voting Machine. Button inserted

6 Made it mandatory for MLAs and MPs to declare the source of unaccounted assets.

7 We will change our India

The purpose of this program is to educate senior school children about the challenges facing Indian democracy today. It is about educating them about this. Workshop instructors use video audio and other interactive materials to communicate with young people. In addition, college youth are involved. Their active participation is the purpose of this event. The selected Campus Ambassadors are briefed on the issues ADR is working on. Their role and responsibilities as ADR Campus Representatives are informed.

Evaluation of government performance :

A nationwide survey of more than 2.7 lakh people found that. For 41.34 per cent of the respondents, alcohol, cash and distribution of free items were the key factors behind voting for candidates in an election. Explained from the ADR survey. 86% of the respondents think that candidates with criminal background should not be in Parliament or Assembly. Evaluation of government work Respondents for public transport have given the government a rating of 258%. In addition, 2.50% drinking water facility is rated on the performance of the government. The government's performance in the fight against water pollution is rated 2.51%. 2.48 per cent women empowerment rating. The government has been given a rating of 1.37 per cent to eradicate corruption in the country. The government has received a 1.5% rating on the policy of eradicating terrorism.

Lok Sabha Election 2019

Lok Sabha Election Phase	Total Number of Candidates	Total Number of Candidates Analyzed	Candidates with Declared Criminal Cases	Percentage of Candidates with Declared Criminal Cases	Percentage of Candidates with Declared Serious Criminal Cases	Percentage of Crorepati Candidates	Women Candidates	Percentage of Women Candidates
Phase 1	1279	1266	213	17%	12%	32%	93	7%
Phase 2	1644	1591	251	16%	10%	27%	124	8%
Phase 3	1612	1596	340	21%	14%	25%	143	9%
Phase 4	943	928	210	23%	17%	33%	95	10%
Phase 5	674	668	126	19%	14%	28%	79	12%
Phase 6	979	967	189	20%	15%	32%	83	9%
	7131	7016	1329	19%	13%	29%	617	9%

Table: Summary upto Lok Sabha Phase 6
 Website:-www.adrindia.org, www.myneta.info,

The Lok Sabha elections 2019 were held in six phases. In the first phase, 1279 people had contested the elections out of which 213 persons have been booked. In Phase 2, 1644 people contested the elections and the proportion of candidates with criminal background was 16% The

Lok Sabha elections 2019 were held in six phases. In this election, 7131 candidates were contesting from different constituencies from different political parties, out of which 19 % had criminal background.

Party wise candidates with self-declared criminal case

Party Name	Total number of candidates analyzed	candidates with declared Criminal Cases	% of candidates with declared criminal cases	candidates with declared serious criminal cases	% of candidates with declared serious criminal Cases
Independent	307	34	11%	27	9%
BJP	54	26	48%	18	33%
BSP	49	19	39%	17	35%
INC	46	20	44%	12	26%
SUCI(C)	22	4	18%	4	18%
BHARAT PRABHAT PARTY	20	2	10%	2	10%
PRAGATISHIL SAMAJWADI PARTY (LOHIA)	19	2	11%	2	11%
SHS	16	5	31%	5	31%
AAPKI APNI PARTY (PEOPLES)	14	2	14%	2	14%
AAP	12	3	25%	2	17%
INLD	10	3	30%	2	20%
AITC	10	4	40%	2	20%
AMBEDKARIT E PARTY OF INDIA	8	1	13%	1	13%
HINDUSTHAN NIRMAN DAL	8	4	50%	4	50%
CPI	7	3	43%	3	43%
RPI(A)	7	1	14%		0%
JANNAYAK JANTA PARTY	7	2	29%	2	29%
AIFB	6	2	33%	2	33%
CPI(M)	6	4	67%	4	67%
JAN ADHIKAR PARTY	5	1	20%	1	20%

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Analysis based on assets
 Party wise Crorepati Candidates

Party Name	Number of Candidates Analyzed	No of Crorepatis	Percentage of Crorepati Candidates
Independent	307	71	23%
BJP	54	46	85%
INC	46	37	80%
BSP	49	31	63%
INLD	10	7	70%
AITC	10	7	70%
AAP	12	6	50%
JANNAYAK JANTA PARTY	7	5	71%
PRAGATISHIL SAMAJWADI PARTY (LOHIA)	19	5	26%
PEOPLES PARTY OF INDIA (DEMOCRATIC)	15	4	27%
SHS	16	3	19%
JAI PRAKASH JANATA DAL	4	3	75%

The number of crorepati candidates standing at the party level in the Lok Sabha elections 2019 is given in the table above. In B. J. P. 85% of the candidates were crorepatis. In National Congress party 80% candidates were one crorepatis.

The Aam Aadmi Party's crorepati candidates accounted for 50% of the total. Every political party in India, when distributing tickets, the candidate is considered to be a crorepati. Only those who are rich are given party tickets.

Top 10 Candidates with Highest Assets

S.No.	Name	State	Constituency	Party	Total Assets (Rs)	PAN Given
1	Jyotiraditya M. Scindia	MADHYA PRADESH	GUNA	INC	3,74,56,18,745 374 Crore+	Y
2	Gautam Gambhir	NATIONAL CAPITAL TERRITORY OF DELHI	EAST DELHI	BJP	1,47,15,87,789 147 Crore+	Y
3	Virender Rana	HARYANA	GURGAON	INLD	1,02,58,63,217 102 Crore+	Y
4	Shruti Choudhry	HARYANA	BHIWANI MAHENDRA GARH	INC	1,01,61,18,000 101 Crore+	Y

5	Dushyant Chautala	HARYANA	HISAR	Jannayak Janta Party	76,94,52,859 76 Crore+	Y
6	Deepak Yadav	BIHAR	VALMIKI NAGAR	BSP	56,94,31,975 56 Crore+	Y
7	Maneka Sanjay Gandhi	UTTAR PRADESH	SULTANPUR	BJP	55,69,26,451 55 Crore+	Y
8	Digvijay Singh Chautala	HARYANA	SONIPAT	Jannayak Janta Party	53,18,39,302 53 Crore+	Y
9	Deo Vrat Mishra	UTTAR PRADESH	JAUNPUR	INC	51,09,60,626 51 Crore+	Y
10	Rais Ahmad	HARYANA	GURGAON	BSP	45,93,17,500 45 Crore+	Y

The list of the ten richest candidates in the Lok Sabha elections 2019 is given in the table above. In one, Jyotiraditya Scindia, a candidate from Guna constituency, has assets worth Rs 374 crore.

After this, Gautam Gambhir was the richest millionaire candidate. Political parties and regional parties declare the individual as their candidate.

Top 10 Candidates with Lowest Assets

The details of candidates with lowest assets (excluding zero assets candidate) are given below:

S.No.	Name	State	Constituency	Party Name	Total Assets (Rs)	PAN Given
1	Rangalal Kumar	WEST BENGAL	PURULIA	SUCI(C)	500 5 Hund+	N
2	Sukchand Saren	WEST BENGAL	BANKURA	CPI(ML) Red Star	800 8 Hund+	Y
3	Ashwani	HARYANA	SONIPAT	IND	1,700 1 Thou+	Y
4	Birbaha Hansda	WEST BENGAL	JHARGRAM	Jharkhand Party (Naren)	2,500 2 Thou+	Y
5	Maheswar Hembram	WEST BENGAL	JHARGRAM	Akhil Bhartiya Jharkhand Party	3,800 3 Thou+	N
6	Jitendra Nath Roy	WEST BENGAL	BISHNUPUR	CPI(ML) Red Star	3,850 3 Thou+	Y
7	Parasnath Ram	BIHAR	PURVI CHAMPARAN	Janata Party	5,000 5 Thou+	Y
8	Tarani Roy	WEST BENGAL	BISHNUPUR	IND	9,000 9 Thou+	N
9	Aditi	NATIONAL CAPITAL TERRITORY OF DELHI	NORTH WEST DELHI	IND	18,505 18 Thou+	Y
10	Dheer Singh	NATIONAL CAPITAL TERRITORY OF DELHI	CHANDNI CHOWK	Rashtriya Jansambhavna Party	20,000 20 Thou+	Y

The poorest candidate in the Lok Sabha election 2019 is in the table above. The poorest is observed that the poor candidate who is from the

state of West Bengal was not nominated by the National Party but by the Regional Party.

Analysis based on Other Background Details of Candidates

Overall Education Report

Sr. No.	Education Group	Number of Candidates analyzed
1	Illiterate	10
2	Literate	35
3	5th Pass	24
4	8th Pass	84
5	10th Pass	120
6	12th Pass	167
7	Graduate	184
8	Graduate Professional	127
9	Post Graduate	176
10	Doctorate	22
11	Others	16
12	Not Given	2
13	Total	967

Lok Sabha Election 2019 Candidates Educational Background The number of literate people is 170. The number of candidates who have completed their degree is 184. The number of candidates who have completed their postgraduate

degree is 176. The number of candidates with doctorate is 22. In order for experts to enter politics, their knowledge will definitely benefit the country and democracy

Lok Sabha Election Phase 2019

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4	Phase 4	943	95	10%
5	Phase 5	674	79	12%
6	Phase 6	979	83	9%
		7131	617	9%

The Lok Sabha elections 2019 were held in 6 phases. In the first phase, 93 women candidates were nominated. In the second phase, 124 women were nominated as 8 per cent. In the third round,

143 women were nominated as 9 per cent. In the Lok Sabha elections, 7131 persons were nominated out of which 617 women were nominated.

Conclusions:

The Dinesh Goswami Committee on Electoral Reforms, Inderjit Samiti has recommended for state funding for elections. Which will curb the use of black money. A clean election process requires the regulation of the political party. Therefore, it is imperative that the Election Commission be strengthened effectively. Voters also need to be vigilant against misusing money, gifts and other temptations during elections. Given the reluctance of political parties to curb the criminalization of politics and their increasingly detrimental effects on Indian democracy. Indian courts should now seriously consider banning people with serious criminal charges from contesting elections.

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